

DRUG DOSAGES AND THERAPEUTIC *PANCHKARMA* STANDARDS OF KAUMARBHRITYA IN AYURVEDA: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Equilibrium of *Dosha*'s and freedom from all diseases is called health. For this purpose of health, Acharya's have made Ayurveda. According to Acharya Kashyapa; Kaumarbhriya is one of superior branch among Ashtanga Ayurveda which deals with diseases of children and their practical treatment. In Ayurveda, the *Matra* (dose) of a drug has been mentioned in different treatises out of which Acharya Kashyapa is the pioneer of Ayurvedic pediatric medicine and he has well established the pediatric dosing system. Ayurveda physicians were using different *Matra*'s for different dosage forms and also the dose was fixed according to age and many other factors like *Satva* (mental ability), *Prakriti* (constitution), *Bala* (physical strength) etc. In Ayurveda treatment is chiefly divided into two procedures *Shamana* and *Shodhana chikitsa*. In *Shamana chikitsa* we control and manage *dosha* in body itself which includes *Deepana*, *Pachana* etc. and in *Shodhana chikitsa* is mainly for cleansing the body toxins i.e. cleansing the

prakopita doshas which mainly included *Panchkarma* therapy. In present situation *Panchkarma* therapy looks difficult in pediatric practice because lack of knowledge about dosages, their mode of action and complication. Acharya Kashyapa explained all the *Panchkarma* procedure in details. This review article is related to pediatric drug dosages from different Ayurveda classics and gives utility of specific therapeutic *Panchkarma* procedure and their mode of action in pediatrics patient to strengthening immune system, restoring balance and well being.

KEYWORDS: Kaumarbhriya, Dose, *Matra*, *Shamana*, *Shodhana*, *Panchakarma*.

INTRODUCTION

Patient's treatment methods according to Ayurveda are broadly classified as, *Daiva-vyapashraya* (psychotherapy) and *Yukti-vyapashraya* (physical interventions). *Daivavyapashraya* (Psychotherapy) includes chanting of specific *mantra's* worshipping specific gods, performing *yagya* etc. Second treatment is based on drug therapy. Ayurvedic classics consider drug a very important patient management tool in the hands of physician or a therapist. This tool needs to be handled judiciously, if not done so it is likely to prove injurious or sometimes fatal to the life of patient who receiving it. Acharya Charka while discussing different aspects of drugs and drug therapy says even a poison is an effective drug if used judiciously, where as injudicious use of even nectar can prove harmful. Principle of treatment in children according to Acharya Kashyapa:

“न त्वेव बालस्य विशोषणं हितं नैवाति संशोधनरक्तमोक्षणे।

स्निग्धैः सुशीतैर्मधुरैरदाहिभिस्तत्रोपचारोऽशनलेपसेचनैः॥”

(*Kashyapa Sutrasthana 27/66*)^[1]

For children neither desiccation nor excessive cleansing measures and bloodletting is beneficial. They should be treated only by oral medications, ointments and irrigation with those drugs which are *Snigdha*(unctuous), *Shita* (cold), *Madhura* (sweet) and *Adahi* (do not produce burning sensation). Acharya's (Ancient Ayurveda physicians) have given a general guideline regarding the dose of *Churna* (herbal powder), *Kalka* (paste), *Kashaya* (decoction), *Ghrita* etc. In pediatric age group most physicians find intricacy while prescribing medicine. In ancient era two different methods of measuring the objects were in use called *Magadha Mana* and *Kalinga Mana* (Both are Ayurvedic metric system). To fix on *Matra* (dose) the proportion of different substances like *Amalaki* (Gooseberry), *Kola* (jajube fruit), *Vidanga* (false black paper), *Anjali* (handfull), *Anguli* (Phalanges) etc. was in practice. As the period progressed, this *Mana's* (Measurements) were replaced by milligrams, grams and milliliter etc. It took a long period from ancient era to modern era for getting these dose transformed into current metric system. In clinical practice sometimes it is found that, though the medicine was selected properly according to condition but still physician do not get expected result in particular cases. The main reason behind it may be due to negligence towards classical dose and its proper understanding. This article is aimed to understand the view of ancient sages related to pediatric drug doses from different Ayurveda classics. *Matra* (Dose) is the full measure of anything or measure of any kind of quantity, size, duration, number, degree etc. Posology is the branch of pharmacology and therapeutics concerned with a

determination of the doses of remedies. Drug is a "Natural or synthetic substance which when taken by a human being affects its functioning or structure, and is used in the diagnosis, mitigation, treatment or prevention of a disease or relief of discomfort is called legal drug or medicine. Dose is the quantity of medicine prescribed to be taken at one time. Modern medicines are given in the form of syrup, injections, drops, tablets etc. for the easy administration, palatability and efficacy of drug. Similarly in Ayurveda, *Panchavidha* (5 types); *Shadvidha* (6 types); *Saptavidha* (7 types) *Kashaya Kalpanas* (Drug preparation methods) are described in the section of different dosage forms and these different dosage forms are pre-arranged to adjust the dose and to solve the issues of palatability and potency. Acharaya Charaka was very much conscious about the palatability and potency of drug so while describing the dose of child he said that the medicine which we are going to use for child should be *Madhura-rasatmaka* medicated in the form of *kashaya* (decoction) and given with milk.^[2] These *kalpana*'s are enlisted below.

Table No. 1: Various *Kalpana* according to different Acharya.

Sr. No.	Acharya	<i>Kalpana</i> (Form of medicine)
1	Sharangadhara	<i>Swarasa</i> (juice), <i>Kalka</i> (paste), <i>Kwatha</i> (decoctions), <i>Hima</i> (cold infusion), <i>Phanta</i> (hot infusion)
2	Charaka	<i>Swarasa</i> , <i>Kalka</i> , <i>Shrita</i> (decoctions), <i>Shita</i> (cold infusion), <i>Phanta</i>
3	Shushruta	<i>Swarasa</i> , <i>Kalka</i> , <i>Kwatha</i> , <i>Hima</i> , <i>Phanta</i> , <i>Kshirapaka</i> (milk boiled with the drugs)
4	Kashyapa	<i>Churna</i> , <i>Shitakashaya</i> (cold infusion), <i>Swarasa</i> , <i>Abhishava</i> (fermented drinks), <i>Phanta</i> , <i>Kalka</i> , <i>Kwatha</i>

Dose According to Kashyapa Samhita

Among the entire Ayurveda treatise, Kashyapa Samhita is first which placed the Kaumarbhritya (Pediatric) as First branch in eight branches of Ayurveda. According to Acharya Kashyapa, disease is the root cause of troubles and medicine is cause of pleasure. The medicines when used properly it becomes nectar and improperly used drug acts like a poison so, every physician should have the knowledge of disease, drugs as well as dose. Acharya Kashyapa also described specific doses in different *Kalpana* for different pediatric age group.

Table No. 2: Dose of *Ghrta Kalpana* according to Kashyapa samhita.

Sr. No	Age	<i>Matra</i> (Dose)
1.	Immediately after birth	<i>Kolasthimatra</i>
2.	5 th day	Slightly more than <i>Kolasthimatra</i>

3.	10-20 th days	<i>Kolardhamatra</i>
4.	1 month	<i>Kolamatra</i>
5.	2 month	Slightly more than <i>Kola</i>
6.	3 month	Two <i>Kola Pramana</i>
7.	4 month	Equal to dry <i>Amalaki</i> (Indian gooseberry) fruit
8.	5-6 month	Fresh <i>Amalaki</i> matra

Table No. 3: Dose of *Churna Kalpana* according to *Kashyapa samhita*.

Sr. No.	<i>Churna</i> (Powder)	<i>Matra</i> (Dose)
1.	<i>Deepaniya Churna</i> (Appetizer powder)	<i>Agraparanguli grahya</i> (The quantity of drug held between fore phalanges of fingers of hand)
2.	<i>Jeevaniya</i> (Longevity enhancer) and <i>Sanshamaniya churna</i> (Pacifying powder)	Double of <i>Deepaniya Churna Matra</i>
3.	<i>Vamama</i> (Emetic) and <i>Virechana</i> (Purgative)	<i>Churna</i> Half of <i>Deepaniya Churna Matra</i>

Table No. 4: Dose of *Kashaya Kalpana* according to *Kashyapa samhita*.

Sr. No.	<i>Kashaya</i> (Decoction)	<i>Matra</i> (Dose)
1.	<i>Dosha Nashaka Kashaya</i> (<i>Vata, Pitta, Kapha</i> eradicating Decoctions)	2 <i>Prasrita</i> (192 ml)
2.	<i>Vamaka</i> and <i>Virechaka Kashaya</i>	1 <i>Prasrita</i> (96 ml)
3.	<i>Deepaniya</i> and <i>Sanshamaniya Kashaya</i>	2 <i>Prasrita</i> (192 ml)

Table No. 5: Dose of *Kalka Kalpana* according to *Kashyapa samhita*.

Sr. No.	<i>Kalka</i>	<i>Matra</i> (Dose)
1.	<i>Deepaniya Kalka</i>	1 <i>Karsh</i> (12 grams)
2.	<i>Jeevaniya</i> and <i>Sanshamaniya Kalka</i>	2 <i>Karsh</i> (24grams)
3.	<i>Vamaka</i> and <i>Virechaka Kalka</i>	½ <i>Karsha</i> (6 grams)

Samanya aushadhi matra* according to *Kashyapa Samhita

For *Navajata Shishu* (newborn) *Matra* of *Ghrita* (ghee) is told as *Vidangaphalatulya*, afterwards the dose is gradually increased. The dose of *Ghrita* can be increased up to *Amalakiphala* (size of fruit of Gooseberry) but not more than that.

Dose According to *Sushruta Samhita*

In the context of classification of age, Acharya *Sushruta* has classified the age as *Balya* (young age), *Madhya* (adult) and *Vridhdha* (old age) and the group *Balya* has been further divided into *Kshirada* (child dependant only on milk), *Kshirannada* (child dependent upon milk and cereals) and *Annada* (depending upon cereals). Acharya *Sushruta* has given dose for *Kshirada*, *Kshirannada* and *Annada Avastha* which are enlisted below.^[3]

Table No. 6: Age specific different drug doses according to Sushruta samhita.

Sr. No.	Age group	Matra (Dose)
1.	<i>Kshirada</i> (up to 1 year)	<i>Anguliparvadvaya grahya</i> (The quantity of medicine which adheres in between the apex of thumb and index finger. Honey or ghee should be used as <i>Anupana</i> .)
2.	<i>Kshirannada</i> (1-2 year)	<i>Kolasthi</i> (Medicines in the form of paste shall be given in an amount of size of seed of a kernel of a jujube fruit)
3.	<i>Annada</i> (2-16 years)	<i>Kola Matra</i> (Equal to jujube fruit)

Dose According to Acharya Sharangadhara

Sharangadhara Samhita (13th AD) is one of the authentic book of Ayurveda where *Mana* (science of measurement) is discussed in detail. The classic has established the dose from minimal to maximum i.e. from *Paramanu* (atom) to *Tula* (100 *pala*). The dose is given in simplified measures as a *Ratti* and *Masha* which can be easily converted into current metric system. This is the great contribution of sharangdhara samhita in Ayurveda posology E.g. 1 *Ratti* = 125mg.^[4,5]

Table No. 7: Dose Acc. to Acharya Sharangdhara is given below.

Sr. No.	Age	Matra (Dose)
1.	1 Month	1 <i>Ratti</i> = 125 mg (<i>Churna, Kalka, Avaleha</i> formulation with ghee, honey, milk, sugar as <i>Anupana</i>)
2.	2 Months - 1 Year	Increase by 1 <i>Ratti</i> every month up to 12 Months (1 <i>Ratti</i> to 12 <i>Ratti</i> = 125 mg to 1.5 gm)
3.	1 Year - 16 Years	Increase by 1 <i>Masha</i> (1.5 gm) every year (1 <i>Masha</i> to 16 <i>Masha</i> =1.5 gm to 24 gms)
4.	For, <i>Kwatha</i> (Decoction)	It should be given four times of above calculated dose as per age.

Drug doses mentioned in different classics of Ayurveda are given with respect to ancient systems of *Mana* (Measurement). In ancient era the technology was not evolved, so the framework of measurement was experience based and objects in custom employ were taken as measure of weight eg. *Badariphalatulya, Amalakiphalatulya, Vidangaphalatulya* etc. Most of the Ayurveda scholars are amazed regarding these *Manas*. The biggest query is arises in mind of physician that weight of *Vidanga/Amalaki* should be taken into account or medicine should be taken same as the shape of fruit of *Vidanga/Amalaki* etc. The exact weight cannot be assumed because *Amalaki, Kola* etc. fruits have different varieties and also the weight varies with different regions and also all the fruits do not carry same weight. This is the situation these days because of wide genetically modified variants available in the market. In

olden days this was not the case. May be *Kola* has remained the same even in current times, the only standard they had was to take it in the dosage of common fruits available in every region. So only approximation could be expected with the ancient dosing system and not accuracy and with the help of own logic physician should manage doses for different patient. Acharya's were clear in their ways. It is to be taken in the size or weight of the particular drug and not *Amla* or *Vidanga* as such. The word "tulya" (equivalent) is being used in quotation, so it becomes more specific to consider shape/proportion of the particular object rather than weight. Still this opinion can vary from person to person; so a wise physician should use *Yukti* (logic) in such cases. For *Churnamatra*, this is clarified by Acharya Kashyapa which comments whenever *Mana* (measurement) like *Prakuncha* needs to be referred in drug administration then the *Pramana* (Anthropometrical measurements) of the person who is going to consume the medicine should be considered. Also, dose can be minimized in *Alpa Bala* (less body strength) and *Alpa Satva* (less mental strength) child.^[6] Acharya Sharangadhara and Yogaratnakara guidelines are more comprehensible and acceptable as the dose mentioned in these Samhita can be easily converted into current metric system. The dose is given considering the compound formulation and commonly used *Kalpana* (formulation) are discussed with their age specific dose. This helps to counteract the uncertainty about pediatric drug doses especially for Ayurveda formulation. Sharangadhara Samhita dose fixation guideline is widely accepted in Ayurveda dosing system. When adult dose is not defined, the general guidelines given by Acharya's considering the contents of the drug and other parameters such as *Dosha*, *Desha*, *Kala*, *Vaya*, *Agnibala* etc. physician has to calculate the dose. Some of the adult doses of different *Kalpana* are shown below^[7]

Table No. 8: Dose of different *Kalpana* according to Sharangadhara Samhita.^[8]

Sr No.	<i>Kalpana</i>	<i>Matra</i> (Dose)
1	<i>Churna</i> (herbal powder)	1 <i>Karsha</i> (12 grams)
2	<i>Vati</i> (pills)	1 <i>Karsha</i> (12 grams)
3	<i>Swarasa</i> (juice)	Fresh ½ <i>pala</i> -2 <i>Tola</i> (27 ml.), Extracted after boiling-1 <i>Pala</i> (48ml)
4	<i>Avaleha</i> (Confections)	1 <i>Pala</i> (48 ml)
5	<i>Kwatha</i> (Decoction)	2 <i>Pala</i> (96 ml)
6	<i>Ghrita/Taila</i> (oil)	1 <i>Pala</i> (48 ml)
7	<i>Asava Arishta</i> (Fermented liquids)	2 <i>Pala</i> (96 mi)

Various factors affecting drug dose

1. *Dosha* (Physical constitution and nature of disease)
2. *Dushya* (Part vitiated in body)

3. *Bala* (Body strength)
4. *Kala* (Time of administration)
5. *Agni* (Appetite/Digestive fire)
6. *Prakriti* (Genetic factors and body constitution)
7. *Vaya* (Age, body weight, surface area)
8. *Vyadhi* (Disease)
9. *Dravya* (Drug)
10. *Koshtha* (Biological membrane/distribution)
11. *Satva* (Emotional quotient)
12. *Satmya* (Tolerance)
13. *Rogavastha* (Pathological state)
14. *Prayoga Marga* (Route of administration)
15. *Desha* (Environment)
16. *Ahara Vyavastha* (Diet and dietetic practices)
17. *Anupana* (Mediator/Catalyst)

STANDARDS OF PANCHKARMA TREATMENT IN KAUMARBHRITYA

Larger part of the pediatric illness is *Samanoushadha Sadhya*. Indeed, even medications with *Mridu* and *Madhyam Veerya* act successfully in youngsters. This can be credited to their *Mridukaayata* and *Alpaveeryata*. Those illnesses which endure even after *Samana Chikitsa* must be treated with *Shodhana Chikitsa*. *Panchkarma* treatment is the more grounded technique for end of *Doshas* by eliminating them out of body. However it has been referenced that, more grounded restorative methods should not be utilized in youngsters but rather a changed *Panchkarma* could be certainly utilized.^[9]

1. *Snehana*

Snehana is discretionary in *Ksheerada* and *Ksheerannada* youngsters as they generally remain *Snigdha* by consistent utilization of *Ghrita* and *Ksheera*. By this reference we can say that extra and formal *Snehana Vidhi* isn't needed in that frame of mind up to the 2 year old enough. If at all *Snehana* becomes fundamental as in lactation disappointment, taking care of challenges, and so forth it tends to be applied like *Achchapana* and *Vichaarana*. *Bahya* (outer application) as well as *Abhyantara* (inner) *Snehapana* has been prosecuted in kids. Modest quantity of *Snehana* in kids goes about as an anabolic (*Brimhana*) in nature increments general imperativeness as well as intellectual ability. *Snehana* ought to be given in exact

moment amount to *Ksheerapa* kid due to pre-strength of *Kapha Dosha*. ex. In *Bahya Prayoga-Bala Taila Pichu Prayoga, Raja Taila, Kustha Taila*. In *Aabhyantera Prayoga-Kumar Kalyana Ghrita, Samvardhana Ghrita, Brahmi Ghrita*. Kashyapa told that oleation treatment is contraindicated to the pregnant ladies, conveyed ladies, baby or milk diet, having gotten consume.^[10]

2. Swedana

Acharya Kashyapa told that eight kinds of *Swedana* to the kids from birth onwards thinking about the time span and condition of the sickness and strength of body. However the *Swedana* has been expressed contraindicated in kids in common practice. *Swedana* to be performed solely after covering the eyes with leaves of *Kumuda, Utpal* and *Padma* or a delicate material. Acharya Kashyap has referenced milder types of *Swedana* as *Hasta Swedana* (up to four month old) and *Pata Sweda* (as long as six years old).^[11] The *Avasthika Swedana* is valuable to the started and medium constructed kids, particularly to the youngsters whose body is seized with the sickness of cold (*Sheeta Guna Nidanas*).

3. Vamana

For the most part *Vamana* is contraindicated in youngsters. In spite of this reality, a lot of references can be referred to in old style texts as well as in kashyapasamhita demonstrating *Vamana* in youngsters. It is the primary most system acted in *Jatamatra Paricharya* of new-conceived. Any left-over liquid or mucous present in the oral hole can be let out by giving ghee and *Saindhava Lavana* for prompting spewing. *Vamana* can be managed effectively in kids because of *Kapha Dosha* predominance, so *Vamana* is best for *Kapha Rogas* of a kid. Acharya Kashyapa cautions that *Vamana* is contraindicated in underneath 6 year old enough however one more well-qualified assessment that assuming *Vamana* given to a little youngster might cause entanglement like *Kustha, Netraroga, Aruchi* and so on, in this way, consistently give *Vamana* in kids following 6 years. In instances of *Vamana* being the main choice, *Sadhya Vamana* (*Sadhya Snehana + Mridu Vamana*) Preceding *Vamana*, the stomach of the child to be loaded up with bosom milk (In *Ksheerada* and *Ksheerannada*). In *Annada, Laghu* and *Tanu Peya* with *Ghrita* can be utilized rather than *Stanya*. The youngster who himself launches milk after continued nursing, to him the *Daiva* and *Manusi* infection won't ever burden.^[12] While portraying *Chikitsa* of *Ksheeralasaka* and in *Kapha Dushita Stanya Vyadhi*.

4. Virechana

Virechana to be acted in youngsters if all else fails; any remaining options neglecting to fix an illness. This *Karma* to be administrated with intense watchfulness as there lies a strong risk of parchedness which the kids are exceptionally inclined to. *Mridu Virechana Aoushadha (Trivrit)*, *Sukhvirechna Aoushadha (Chaturungula)* can be strategically applied. In Charaka, *Mridu Virechana* by *Aaragvadha* is educated in youngsters with respect to mature gathering between 4-12 years. In Kashyapa *Phakka Chikitsa* it is said that *Snehana* in youngsters to be finished with *Kalyanaka Ghrita* or *Shatpala Ghrita* or *Amrita Ghrita* for multi day followed by *Shodhana* with *Trivrit Ksheera*. By the above references we can say that *Mridu Virechana* is shown in kids.

5. Basti

Acharya Kashyapa says; in kids *Basti Karma* likes nectar (*Amrita*) in light of the fact that because of this work *Samsodhana*, *Samshamana*, *Samgrahana*, *Vajikarana*, *Brumhana*, *Vali Palitnashana*, and *Vayah-sthapana*. *Basti* can be utilized generously in kids, remembering the particular in portion. *Brihatrayis* grant the organization of *Basti* from 1 year old enough. In Kashyapasamhita, this has been examined in an intricate way. Acharya Kashyapa has fixed models to start the *Basti* strategy in a youngster as follows. Youngster, who has finished neonatal period and ready to creep, sit and remain without help. Youngster, who can take strong food day to day or who has begun weaning from bosom milk. *Basti*, oral utilization of oleaginous substance, sedation and scouring of unguents particularly in youngsters seized with sickness of *Vata*. In any of the sickness assuming that *Vata Dosha* is predominant in the pathogenesis of the illness or sickness in persistent state there we can give *Basti* therapy.^[13]

6. Nasya

Ksheerapa kid *Nasya Karma* to be finished by *Katu Taila* or *Saindhavyukta Ghrita*. This ought to be gone on till total vanishing of the infection. Drop by drop meds ought to be ingrained over nostrils and afterward squeezed for quite a while. This prompts liquefaction of *Kapha* and thusly, eliminates the infection.^[14] Pushing the utilization of *Nasya* to kids over long term old enough could have been finished based on understanding the advancement of Para-nasal sinuses. Advancement of para-nasal sinuses goes on over the course of growing up. Upon entering the world, just maxillary, ethmoidal and sphenoidal sinuses are framed. Radiological presence of front facing sinus shows up at long term. Ethmoidal sinus totally

creates by around long term old enough. So, *Nasya* is contraindicated less than 8 years old; however *Pratimarsha Nasya* could be given in all age gatherings.

DISCUSSION

In Modern science different formulae like Young's Formula, Dilling's Formula etc. are in use to calculate dose according to age. In order to produce drugs optimal effect, a drug must be present in an appropriate concentration at its site of action. The various steps involved in the pharmacokinetics are the concentration of the drug at the target site depends upon the dose or amount of drug,

1. Liberation or release of active ingredient from the pharmaceutical formulation
2. Absorption from the site of delivery into blood circulation.
3. Distribution into various fluids compartment and tissues of the body.
4. Transfer of drugs across all membranes largely depends on their dose or concentration, molecular size and shape, solubility at the site of absorption, degree of ionization and relative lipid solubility.
5. Metabolization of the drug mostly in the liver.
6. The water soluble drug is largely excreted in the urine while ionized lipid soluble agents may be stored in the body tissues.^[15]
7. Drops formulation are preferred in young infant due to small volume of the medicine to be administered. In preschool children, syrup or suspension formulation is usually given. Dispersible tablets or mouth dissolving tablets can be given to children above 2-3yrs of age. Most school going children should be able to swallow tablets or capsules but at times even an adolescent child may refuse to take a tablet. Some children are extremely prone to vomit when a medicine is given to them.

There are some formulae to calculate the pediatric doses are given below:-

- A) Up to 2 yrs - **Fried's Rule** Dose = Adult dose x Age in month / 150
- B) Above 2 yrs - **Clark's Rule** Dose = Adult dose x weight in pounds / 150
- C) **Young's formula** = Adult dose x Age in year / Age + 12

All childhood diseases occur due to the vitiation of *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha Doshas* and *Panchkarma* (i.e. *Vaman*, *Virechana*, *Basti*, *Nasya* etc) therapy help in purification of the whole body by eliminating harmful toxins. *Panchkarma* help to pacify these *Doshas* vitiation strengthens immune system and increase acceptability of body to various therapeutic regimens. Pediatric *Panchkarma* has been prime and leading modality of treatment and

classics clearly mention about its indications and contraindications. *Panchkarma* can be carefully implemented in *Swatantra* child or *Partantra* child by considering *Bala*, *Desha*, *Kala*, etc. All *Panchkarma* are systematically explained in classics with special reference of child. Prevention of complications is very important in case of Pediatric *Panchkarma* procedure.

CONCLUSION

Acharya Kashyapa quotes that “The drug, which does not destroy the patient’s strength but destroy the disease potency, should be used till complete eradication of disease.” In continuation to this drug should also be selected after observing various factors like *Dosha*, *Agni*, *Bala*, *Vaya*, *Vyadhi*, *Kostha*, *Prakriti*, *Satmya*, *Desha*, *Kala*, etc. Dose of medicine selected for the treatment of disease should not be too excess or too low. So, a wise physician anticipating complete cure of disease should have knowledge about classical dose of medicine according to age. Also some doses mentioned in classics seem to be higher in today’s perspective. The reason behind this may be the *Bala* and *Satva* of children in ancient period was different as compared to today’s generation.

Panchkarma as *Shodhana Chikitsa* is an integral part of Ayurveda, acts as preventive as well as curative measure and improves the body immunity and thus helps in maintaining the good physical and mental health. In Ayurvedic literature, full description of *Panchkarma* in Pediatrics is available but it is not practised due to lack of practical exposure along with improper understanding of principles of *Panchkarma* in Pediatrics. *Panchkarma* is crucial part of Ayurvedic management; it can’t be ignored in Pediatric practice.

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